

STEPS OF PRODUCT PRICING SYSTEM

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Annotation: Setting a price for a product or service can be a challenge, as many variables factor into determination of a price. Additionally, accurate pricing can be based on values that can be difficult to know without extensive research. As a result, many companies make costly mistakes when incorrectly attempting to price a product or service.

Keywords: price, evaluation, technology, trade, calculation, account.

INTRODUCTION

A large portion of pricing is determined by the customer segment a company is targeting or the market it is entering. It is important to have strongly supported and reliable knowledge of a targeted customer segment before determining price. The Extension publication *Starting a New Business: Pre-Launch Research*, EC495, can help with preliminary business research. It will help identify the characteristics, demographics, and buying habits of the targeted customer. It is strongly suggested that this document, or other materials on business and customer research, be used as a reference to the pricing tactics introduced in this circular.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

When selling a product with a positive contribution margin there is a point at which revenue is equal to expenses — this is the Break-Even Point. Any sales after this point represent profit for the company. It is important for companies to know this point, as it will help determine realistic sales projections and strategies¹.

There are many different kinds of fixed and variable costs. When calculating price, it is important to have a list of all costs (both fixed and variable) that go into a product. Failure to do so can lead to inaccurate pricing, and even lost profitability.

Some examples of both fixed and variable costs are:

¹ Nagle, T., Hogan, J., Zale, J. (2013). *The Strategy and tactics of pricing: A guide to growing more profitably* (5th ed.). Pearson Education Limited.

Fixed Costs

- Research and development
- Equipment (e.g., machinery)
- Indirect labor (i.e., used for general company operations)
- Insurance
- Rent
- Some forms of marketing (brand establishment, advertisements, etc.)
- Web hosting

Variable Costs

- Raw Materials
- Direct labor (i.e., used to assemble a product)
- Some marketing expenses (commissions, rebates, etc.)
- Credit card fees
- Shipping

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Break-even analysis can help determine if a price point is favorable for a product or service. For example, if a company considers a certain price point, conducts a break-even analysis, and finds that the break-even point requires more sales than total potential customers, this indicates that profitability is unlikely with this selected price. While a break-even analysis will not directly be used to determine price, it does serve as an effective method for checking whether a proposed price will lead to favorable outcomes for a company.

The first step for completing a break-even analysis is to compile all costs for the product or service. These costs should be divided into variable costs and fixed costs. Calculate the contribution margin (as described in the section above) using variable costs and the proposed price. Next, divide total fixed costs by the contribution margin. This will determine the number of sales required to break even. An example of calculating break-even analysis is demonstrated below:

Example: Break-Even Analysis

A high school student recently started a business making custom airbrushed mailboxes. She is running this business out of her parents' garage, and does not need a dedicated space or real estate. It takes this student 1.5 hours to paint a single mail-box, and she would like to earn \$10/hour for her labor.

The student would like to break even after one year. After factoring in other commitments, she believes she can sell 20 mailboxes in her first year at \$70 per mailbox (she is a full-time student, and has many other commitments).

The first step was to list all fixed and variable costs. These were as follows²:

² Smith, T. (2012). *Pricing strategy: Setting price levels, managing price discounts, & establishing price structures*. South-Western, Cengage Learning.

Fixed Costs

Business license registration – \$40
Airbrush and parts – \$150
Airbrush painting class – \$50
Reusable stencils – \$10
Marketing photography – \$100
Total Fixed Costs – \$350

Variable Costs

Mailbox – \$20/box
Paint – \$5/unit
Labor – \$15/unit
Shipping – \$10/unit sold
Total Variable Costs – \$50/mailbox

Value-Based Pricing

The most effective way to price an object is based on the value it creates for customers and the customers' perceived worth. Referred to as Value-Based Pricing, it requires significant knowledge of a company's customers and their needs.

To calculate value-based pricing, one must compile all value propositions created by the product and calculate a monetary amount for each. Value propositions may include items such as the cost to replace a current product, labor, or costs prevented by a new product, or any other values created by the product for its end user. While other factors can indirectly affect price (e.g., customer knowledge of a product, competitive landscape, etc.), price should still be directly proportional to the value created.

Retail Pricing

There are many instances when a business will not sell directly to a customer. The business will instead sell products to a retail business, which in turn will sell them to customers. Although retail businesses do not have the manufacturing costs described in earlier examples, they will have labor and overhead costs that must be covered when setting prices. As a result, they do not pay the same price a retail customer does. The term Wholesale Price refers to the price a retailer pays for a product. Retail Price refers to the price that a retailer sets for its customers. Generally, these two prices are directly related. The retail price is usually determined by multiplying the product's wholesale price by a set percentage. The term Markup is used to refer to this relationship.

CONCLUSION

Accurate and effective pricing is a critical step for a business to reach profitability. Pricing strategies should be developed for all products and services and should rely heavily on understanding the customers' needs and perceived values. This publication serves as an early guide to pricing by introducing important concepts and terms, pre-senting methods for determining pricing, and discussing various business objectives and their effects on pricing.

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